

On Hyper Generalized Quasi Einstein Manifolds

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Abstract: In this paper its proved three theorems about global properties of hyper generalized quasi-Einstein manifolds.

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§1. Introduction

The notion of quasi Einstein manifold was introduced in a paper [8] by M.C.Chaki and R.K.Maity. According to them a non-flat Riemannian manifold $(M^n, g), (n \geq 3)$ is defined to be a quasi Einstein manifold if its Ricci tensor S of type $(0, 2)$ satisfies the condition

$$S(X, Y) = ag(X, Y) + bA(X)A(Y) \quad (1)$$

and is not identically zero, where a, b are scalars $b \neq 0$ and A is a non-zero 1-form such that

$$g(X, \xi_1) = A(X), \quad \forall X \in TM, \quad (2)$$

where, ξ_1 is a unit vector field.

In such a case a, b are called the associated scalars. A is called the associated 1-form. Such an n -dimensional manifold is denoted by the symbol $(QE)_n$.

Again, U.C.De and G.C.Ghosh defined generalized quasi Einstein manifold. A non-flat Riemannian manifold is called a generalized quasi Einstein manifold if its Ricci-tensor S of type $(0,2)$ is non-zero and satisfies the condition

$$S(X, Y) = ag(X, Y) + bA(X)A(Y) + cB(X)B(Y), \quad (3)$$

where a, b, c are non-zero scalars and A, B are two 1-forms such that

$$g(X, \xi_1) = A(X) \quad \text{and} \quad g(X, \xi_2) = B(X) \quad (4)$$

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with ξ_1, ξ_2 unit vectors which are orthogonal, i.e,

$$g(\xi_1, \xi_2) = 0. \quad (5)$$

This type of manifold are denoted by $G(QE)_n$.

In [16], H.G. Nagaraja introduced the concept of $N(k)$ -mixed quasi Einstein manifold and mixed quasi constant curvature. A non flat Riemannian manifold (M^n, g) is called a $N(k)$ -mixed quasi Einstein manifold if its Ricci tensor of type $(0, 2)$ is non zero and satisfies the condition

$$S(X, Y) = ag(X, Y) + bA(X)B(Y) + cB(X)A(Y), \quad (6)$$

where a, b, c are smooth functions and A, B are non zero 1-forms such that

$$g(X, \xi_1) = A(X) \quad \text{and} \quad g(X, \xi_2) = B(X) \quad \forall X, \quad (7)$$

with ξ_1, ξ_2 the orthogonal unit vector fields. Such a manifold is denoted by the symbol $N(k) - (MQE)_n$.

The notion of hyper-generalized quasi Einstein manifold has been introduced by A.A.Shaikh, C. Özgür and A.Patra[17] in 2011. An n -dimensional Riemannian manifold (M^n, g) ($n > 2$) is called a hyper generalized quasi-Einstein manifold if its Ricci tensor of type $(0, 2)$ is non zero and satisfies the following condition

$$\begin{aligned} S(X, Y) = & ag(X, Y) + bA(X)A(Y) + c[A(X)B(Y) + A(Y)B(X)] \\ & + d[A(X)D(Y) + A(Y)D(X)] \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

for all $X, Y \in \chi(M)$, where a, b, c and d are real valued, non-zero scalars functions on (M^n, g) . A, B and D are non zero 1-forms such that

$$g(X, \xi_1) = A(X), \quad g(X, \xi_2) = B(X) \quad \text{and} \quad g(X, \xi_3) = D(X), \quad (9)$$

where ξ_1, ξ_2, ξ_3 are three unit vector fields mutually orthogonal to each other at every point on M . Here a, b, c, d are called the associated scalars, A, B, D are called the associated main and auxiliary 1-forms. We denote this type of manifold $(HGQE)_n$.

§2. Preliminaries

From (8) and (9), we get

$$S(X, X) = a|X|^2 + b|g(X, \xi_1)|^2 + 2c|g(X, \xi_1)g(X, \xi_2)| + 2d|g(X, \xi_1)g(X, \xi_3)|, \quad \forall X. \quad (10)$$

Let θ_1 be the angle between ξ_1 and any vector X ; θ_2 be the angle between ξ_2 and any

vector X ; θ_3 be the angle between ξ_3 and any vector X . Then

$$\cos \theta_1 = \frac{g(X, \xi_1)}{\sqrt{g(\xi_1, \xi_1)}\sqrt{g(X, X)}} = \frac{g(X, \xi_1)}{\sqrt{g(X, X)}}$$

as $g(\xi_1, \xi_1) = 1$, and

$$\cos \theta_2 = \frac{g(X, \xi_2)}{\sqrt{g(X, X)}} \quad \text{and} \quad \cos \theta_3 = \frac{g(X, \xi_3)}{\sqrt{g(X, X)}}.$$

If $b > 0$, $c > 0$, we have from (10)

$$(a + b + 2c + 2d)|X|^2 \geq a|X|^2 + b|g(X, \xi_1)|^2 + 2c|g(X, \xi_1)g(X, \xi_2)| + 2d|g(X, \xi_1)g(X, \xi_3)| = S(X, X). \quad (11)$$

Now, contracting (8) over X and Y , we get

$$r = na, \quad (12)$$

where r is the scalar curvature. Since ξ_1, ξ_2 and ξ_3 are orthogonal unit vector fields, therefore $g(\xi_1, \xi_1) = 1$, $g(\xi_2, \xi_2) = 1$, $g(\xi_3, \xi_3) = 1$, $g(\xi_1, \xi_2) = 0$, $g(\xi_1, \xi_3) = 0$ and $g(\xi_2, \xi_3) = 0$.

Again, putting $X = Y = \xi_1$ in (8) we get $S(\xi_1, \xi_1) = a + b$. Putting $X = Y = \xi_2$ in (8) we get $S(\xi_2, \xi_2) = a$. Putting $X = Y = \xi_3$ in (8) we get $S(\xi_3, \xi_3) = a$.

If X is a unit vector field, then $S(X, X)$ is the Ricci-curvature in the direction of X .

Notice that Q is the symmetric endomorphism of the tangent space at each point corresponding to the Ricci-tensor S , where

$$g(QX, Y) = S(X, Y) \quad \forall X, Y \in TM. \quad (13)$$

Let l^2 denote the squares of the lengths of the Ricci-tensor S . Then

$$l^2 = \sum_{i=1}^n S(Qe_i, e_i), \quad (14)$$

where $\{e_i\}$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$ is an orthonormal basis of the tangent space at a point of $(HGQE)_n$.

Now from (8) we get

$$\begin{aligned} S(Qe_i, e_i) &= ag(Qe_i, e_i) + bA(Qe_i)A(e_i) + c[A(Qe_i)B(e_i) + A(e_i)B(Qe_i)] \\ &\quad + d[A(Qe_i)D(e_i) + A(e_i)D(Qe_i)], \end{aligned}$$

i.e.,

$$l^2 = (n - 2)a^2 + (a + b)^2 + 2c^2 + 2d^2. \quad (15)$$

These result will be used in the sequel.

§3. Ricci Semi-symmetric $(HGQE)_n (n > 3)$

Chaki and Maity proved that $(QE)_n (n > 3)$ is Ricci Semi-symmetric if and only if

$$A(R(X, Y)Z) = 0.$$

Let us suppose that $(HGQE)_n (n > 3)$ is Ricci-Semi symmetric. Then

$$A(R(X, Y)Z) = 0. \quad (16)$$

From (16) we get

$$A(Q(X)) = 0, \quad (17)$$

where Q be the symmetric endomorphism of the tangent space at each point corresponding to the Ricci tensor S . Then

$$g(QX, Y) = S(X, Y). \quad (18)$$

Then from (8) we get

$$A(Q(X)) = (a + b)A(X) + cB(X) + dD(X). \quad (19)$$

From (17) and (19) it follows that

$$(a + b)A(X) + cB(X) + dD(X) = 0. \quad (20)$$

Thus we can state the following.

Theorem 3.1 *If a $(HGQE)_n$ is Ricci Semi symmetric than $(a+b)A(X)+cB(X)+dD(X)=0$.*

§4. Sufficient Condition for a Compact Orientable $(HGQE)_n (n \geq 3)$ Without Boundary to be Isometric to a Sphere

In this section we consider a compact, orientable $(HGQE)_n$ without boundary having constant associated scalars a, b, c and d . Then from (11) and (15), it follows that the scalar curvature is constant and so also is the length of the Ricci-tensor.

We further suppose that $(HGQE)_n$ under consideration admits a non-isometric conformal motion generated by a vector field X . Since l^2 is constant, it follows that

$$\mathcal{L}_X l^2 = 0, \quad (21)$$

where \mathcal{L}_X denotes Lie differentiation with respect to X .

Now, it is known ([2], [4], [5], [9], [12], [13], [14], [15]) that if a compact Riemannian manifold M of dimension $n > 2$ with constant scalar curvature admits an infinitesimal non-isometric conformal transformation X such that $\mathcal{L}_X l^2 = 0$ then M is isometric to a sphere. But a sphere is Einstein so that b, c and d vanish which is a contradiction. This leads to the following theorem.

Theorem 4.1 *A compact orientable hyper generalized quasi Einstein manifold $(HGQE)_n$ ($n \geq 3$) without boundary does not admit a non-isometric conformal vector field.*

§5. Killing Vector Field in a Compact Orientable $(HGQE)_n$ ($n \geq 3$) Without Boundary

In this section, we consider a compact, orientable $(HGQE)_n$ ($n \geq 3$) without boundary with a, b, c and d as associated scalars.

It is known [4] that in such a manifold M , the following relation holds

$$\int_M [S(X, X) - |\nabla X|^2 - (\operatorname{div} X)^2] dv \leq 0 \quad \forall X. \quad (22)$$

If X is a killing vector field, then $\operatorname{div} X = 0$ ([4]). Hence (22) takes the form

$$\int_M [S(X, X) - |\nabla X|^2] dv = 0. \quad (23)$$

Let $b > 0, c > 0, d > 0$. Then by (11)

$$(a + b + 2c + 2d)|X|^2 \geq S(X, X). \quad (24)$$

Therefore,

$$(a + b + 2c + 2d)|X|^2 - |\nabla X|^2 \geq S(X, X) - |\nabla X|^2. \quad (25)$$

Consequently,

$$\int_M [(a + b + 2c + 2d)|X|^2 - |\nabla X|^2] dv \geq \int_M [S(X, X) - |\nabla X|^2] dv, \quad (26)$$

and by (23)

$$\int_M [(a + b + 2c + 2d)|X|^2 - |\nabla X|^2] dv \geq 0. \quad (27)$$

If $a + b + 2c + 2d < 0$, then

$$\int_M [(a + b + 2c + 2d)|X|^2 - |\nabla X|^2] dv = 0. \quad (28)$$

Therefore, $X = 0$. This leads to the following.

Theorem 5.1 *If in a compact orientable $(HGQE)_n$ ($n \geq 3$) without boundary and the associated scalars are such that $b > 0, c > 0, d > 0$ and $a + b + 2c + 2d < 0$, then there exists no non-zero killing vector field in this manifold.*

Corollary 5.1 *If in a compact orientable $(HGQE)_n$ ($n \geq 3$) without boundary, and each of the associated scalars a, b, c, d , is greater than zero, then any harmonic vector field X in the $(HGQE)_n$ is parallel and orthogonal to one of the generators of the manifold which makes greatest angle with the vector X .*

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